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Officer's Call

Sesquicentennial Series Article #49 The History of Arlington Cemetery

By David Hudgins

Arlington National Cemetery may be the best known military cemetery in the world. Most people believe it is located in Washington D.C., but it is actually in Alexandria, Virginia. The final resting place for two presidents, thousands of soldiers, the Tomb of the Unknown Soldier, and 25 monuments and memorials, the cemetery's roots date back to the War between the States and have a tarnished beginning.

The property has a history that goes back to the Founding Fathers, but not as a national cemetery. In 1750, Daniel Parke Custis married Martha Dandridge and they had

two children. A few years after the children's birth, Daniel passed away. Martha then married a young army officer named George Washington. Martha and her two children, John Parke Custis and Martha Custis, moved into Washington's home, Mt. Vernon.

In 1778, John Parke Custis purchased a 1,100 acre tract on the Potomac River in Virginia. While serving as an aid to General George Washington, John died from "camp fever."

John's oldest son, George Washington Parke Custis, then inherited the property. In 1802, he moved onto the property that was known as "Mt. Washington." The name was later changed to "Arlington" after the Custis property on Virginia's eastern shores. In 1804, he married Mary Lee "Molly" Fitzhugh and they began to build a larger house. Four children were born in the home; however three died before reaching age three.

The one child that survived was Mary Anna Randolph Custis. In 1831, she married a young military officer by the name of Robert E. Lee. In September 1832, their first son was born at Fort Monroe and named George Washington Custis Lee in honor of her father. In late 1834, Lee was transferred to Washington City and the Lees took up residence at Arlington. This would begin a life of frequent relocation and repeated separation for the military family while Arlington served as the primary home base for almost 30 years. Six more children were born to the couple at Arlington.

Mary's father, George Washington Parke Custis, died in 1857. In his will Mary Anna Custis Lee inherited his estate for life and then the property would pass to her oldest son. Robert E. Lee took two years of military leave to serve as the executor of the Custis estate.

At the beginning of the Civil War in 1861, Virginia, along with four other slave states, voted not to leave the Union. When President Lincoln required Virginia to furnish men to the Union army to suppress the Southern states, Virginia voted to secede. Although Lee had been offered command of the Union army, he resigned because he could not fight against his fellow Virginians. Lee received command of Virginia's military forces on April 22, 1861.

The hills around Arlington were occupied by Union troops in May of 1861. Robert E. Lee would never re-

– Continued on Page 4 –

Features

Page 1: Sesquicentennial Article # 49 - The History of Arlington Cemetery by David Hudgins

Page 3: Commander General's Message

Page 4: The Battle of Lavaca, Texas and Lodge # 36 by David Hudgins

Page 6: Samuel Houston Caldwell by Peter J. D'Onofrio

Page 7: Reunion Medals for Sale, MOS&B on Facebook, Request for Annual Dues

Page 9: Request for Articles for the Officer's Call & Confederate Legacy Fund

Page 10: 78th Annual General Convention Announcement & Arlington National Cemetery Tour

Page 11: Convention Registration Form

Page 12: Convention Agenda

Page 13: Christ Church Tour and Convention Luncheon Presentation

Page 14: National Award Deadline Set....

Page 14: MOS&B Scholarship Announcement

Page 15: Chapter & Society Newsletter Awards

Page 15: Chaplain General's Thoughts - Earnest Prayer by Ray Holder

Page 16: Cousin vs. Cousin (Part 1) - The Melancholy Journey of Robert Gibboney Baldwin by Dr. Mark Denison Baldwin

2014-2016

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The MOS&B *Officer's Call*, a leader among heritage magazines, is published monthly by the Military Order of the Stars and Bars.

The members of the MOS&B are descendants of the Confederate Officer Corps, elected government officials, and appointed governmental officials. We are dedicated to the preservation and education of the memory of our ancestors and the traditional values of our Southern Heritage.

Address all general business or advertising correspondence to MOS&B IHQ, P O Box 18901, Raleigh, NC 27619-1890.

Commander General's Message

One of the ways we can advance our cause is through public speaking. It keeps us in touch with our communities and creates greater understanding for our perspectives on history and our heritage. It also creates an immense amount of good will.

CG Jones poses with teacher and granddaughter Sarah at Montclair School, Los Altos, CA

Several years ago I became a public speaker almost by accident. Or was it? For background, I have 3 granddaughters and my daughter – their mother - is a former school teacher. She had left the field of teaching several years ago to raise her 3 daughters. Later, she would return as a part time teacher's aide for the fifth grade.

The fifth grade is a critical grade because it is the first time that elementary grade students begin to study United States history. On one particular day, my daughter was aiding in a fifth grade class when the subject of the Revolutionary War first came up. She was quick to point out that her father, (that's me!), was an expert on the Revolutionary War because he belonged to the *Sons of the American Revolution*. Further, she said that I would be happy to speak to the class at any time.

Well, when I first heard that I had been "volunteered" I was flabbergasted. I had nothing prepared on the topic and I didn't even know what the right message was for children of that age. But I was a member of the SAR color guard and I did have an authentic looking Continental Soldier's uniform. I also knew that I couldn't say NO to my daughter.

After some research I determined that the ideal topic for school children would be *George Washington and the Battle of Yorktown*. I have refined this presentation over the years and the kids absolutely love it. It is now in a PowerPoint format and its audiences have grown well beyond the schoolroom. I regularly give this same presentation to the DAR, the UDC, SAR, and even the MOS&B. Grown-ups love the presentation every bit as much as the kids do.

But the 5th graders are the most fun to talk to. In many cases they have no idea of how long ago the RW actually was. They also have no idea of the logistics involved to move the Continental Army from New York to Yorktown – a distance of 400 miles - in order to attack Lord General Cornwallis at Yorktown. They also don't know what a *siege* is. But they absolutely love the re-enactment of the surrender ceremony including the surrender of Cornwallis' sword.

The questions the kids ask are priceless. My favorite question is: *Was George Washington still alive when you were younger?* Another (serious) question was: *Why was he so ugly?* It has been so much fun to interact with these young students over the years. Of course, the number of topics that I speak about has grown over the years as well. I now have about a dozen topics for presentation. And, yes, there are some Confederate topics among them. The audiences for my presentations have varied from as little as 20 people to more than 100 people.

Speaking to our schools and to other heritage organizations is personally rewarding. It is also a lot of fun. Many of our members are gifted speakers and already speak to the same organizations that I do. I encourage others to do so. We have a unique culture at MOS&B that is quite different from other heritage organizations. It is so important for people to actually see us and hear our perspectives on history, heritage and culture. There is no better way than through public speaking engagements.
Deo Vindice!

Best Wishes,

Wm. Howard Jones
Commander General

CG Jones poses with students after presentation at Montclair School, Los Altos, CA

CG Jones addresses over 100 - 4th and 5th graders at Farnham School, San Jose, CA

- Sesquicentennial Article # 47 - From Page 1 -

turn to Arlington House. Upon leaving Arlington, Mrs. Lee managed to secure some of the family valuables; however other items, many from Mount Vernon, were looted by Union troops and never returned. She also left behind the family slaves who were scheduled to be freed in 1863 under the terms of her father's will.

Two Union forts were built on the grounds. The mill and fences were used for fire wood. Animals were commandeered and crops destroyed.

In 1862, a war time law was passed requiring that property owned by Confederates in areas occupied by Federal troops pay a tax to the U. S. government. The government required that owners appear in person to pay the tax. Mrs. Lee was the legal owner of Arlington House, but she felt this was a trap to hold her hostage. She sent her cousin to pay the \$92.07 tax, but it was refused. In 1864, the Federal Government confiscated her property. Mrs. Lee would only return one time after the war to Arlington for a last look at her family home.

On June 15, 1864, Secretary of War Edwin Stanton ordered Major General Montgomery Meigs to turn 200 acres around Arlington House into a military cemetery. The first graves were placed in Mrs. Lee's rose garden next to the house. It is believed this was done to prevent the Lees from ever moving back into the house.

After the war neither Robert nor Mary Anna Lee protested that their home had been confiscated by the government. However following their deaths, Custis Lee, the oldest son and now rightful owner of the property, filed a lawsuit against the Federal Government for taking the property. In 1883, the U. S. Supreme Court ruled in his favor. There was then public concern that the bodies on the property would be exhumed. The government approached Mr. Lee about the purchase of all the property. The estate and home were sold by Custis to the U. S. Government for \$150,000.

In June of 1900, the U.S. Congress authorized that a section of Arlington National Cemetery be set aside for the burial of Confederate dead. On March 4, 1906, the government approved a request by the United Daughters of the Confederacy to erect a monument to the Confederate soldiers. The memorial was designed by world-renowned sculptor, Moses Ezekiel, a Confederate veteran and cast by a bronze foundry in Berlin, Germany.

The 32 foot monument is topped with a larger than life figure of a woman representing the South. Her head is crowned with olive leaves and her left hand extends a laurel wreath toward the South for the sacrifice of her fallen sons. Her right hand holds a pruning hook resting on a plow stock. At the feet is a biblical passage "And they shall beat their swords into plow shares and their spears into pruning hooks". There are also life size figures of mythical gods and Confederate soldiers and sailors. The base of the memorial holds the Seal of the Confederacy and a tribute by the United Daughters of the

Confederacy. On the back is a poem by Randolph McKim, a Confederate Chaplin. It reads:

"Not For Fame Or Reward
Not For Place Or For Rank
Not Lured By Ambition
Or Goaded By Necessity
But In Simple
Obedience To Duty
As They Understood It
These Men Suffered All
Sacrificed All
Dared All and Died."

The Confederate monument was dedicated by President Woodrow Wilson on June 4, 1914, the 106th anniversary of Confederate President Jefferson Davis' birthday. A large number of Union and Confederate Veterans attended the event.

There are 482 Confederates buried in a concentric circle around the monument. Moses Ezekiel, the sculptor, is buried at the base. The road in front of Arlington National Cemetery is named Jefferson Davis Highway in his honor.

David Hudgins is a member of the Ellis County Museum Board of Directors and co-founder of the Ellis County Veterans Appreciation Committee. He also serves as Chaplin of the O. M. Roberts Camp #178, Sons of Confederate Veterans. For more information, visit www.omroberts.com.

The Battle of Lavaca Texas and Lodge #36

By David Hudgins

Lavaca, or Port Lavaca as it is now known, is located on Matagorda Bay in deep South Texas. It is located about as far from the Civil War fighting that was taking place in the other southern states as anyone could

get and still be in the Confederacy.

There were no plantations, forts, or slaves in this area. To protect the fishing and small port town, Captain Daniel Shea had organized a small, poorly equipped home guard unit, consisting mainly of older men unfit for service in the Confederate army. Because several members from the home guard were sick with yellow fever, members from the Lavaca Masonic Lodge #36 volunteered to take their place. Who would want to capture this out of the way fishing community? There would be no real advantage gained.

On October 31, 1862, two Federal gunboats arrived and demanded the surrender of Lavaca. When the answer "No" was received, the gunboats started firing over 250 cannon rounds into the homes and businesses of Lavaca. Luckily most of the women, children, sick and elderly were evacuated before the bombardment began. The men from the Masonic Lodge #36 fought like veteran soldiers. The women risked their lives to supply food and coffee to their men. Captain Shea and his men were able to stop the Federals from making landfall. After a few hours the Union gunboats left the bay. One of the men from the lodge who was manning a port gun later stated, "This will be the last time a Northern fleet would slip into a Southern harbor." His name was Edgar C. Singer, a 6'3" gunsmith, originally from Ohio and the nephew of Isaac Singer, inventor of the first commercial sewing machine. Within days, Singer started experimenting with small charges of gunpowder in a water filled barrel. He quickly learned the power of the underwater bombs.

Needing help to finance his invention, Singer turned to his lodge. The leader of the lodge, Dr. John Fretwell, liked what he saw and became Singer's partner. Singer and Fretwell designed a cylinder shaped, water-tight metal canister of gunpowder with a spring-loaded detonating rod. The two men decided to demonstrate their bomb or torpedo, as it was known at that time, to Captain Shea. An old boat hull in the bay was chosen as the target. When the torpedo detonated, the boat was demolished.

Captain Shea was so impressed that he ordered Singer to report to CSA General John Magruder in Houston. By the time Singer and Fretwell arrived, General Magruder was involved in plans to retake Galveston Island from the Federals. When he was told why the two men were there to see him, he was skeptical of the idea. However, he ordered for the men to receive 25 pounds of gunpowder for a demonstration.

On December 31, 1862, General Magruder launched an attack on the island and reclaimed Galveston for the Confederacy. He was now ready to see this new gadget device. The demonstration was held in Houston's Buffalo Bayou. Singer and Fretwell submerged the torpedo about two feet under water and then had an old boat towed across the area. When the boat hit the detonating rod, the boat was blown apart. General

Magruder was very impressed and ordered the two men to report to Major General Dabney H. Maury who was commanding the Gulf District in Mobile, Alabama.

After a demonstration there and approval from the War Department in Richmond, Singer and Fretwell were sent back to Lavaca to start building torpedoes. The two men knew that they would need help. Once again they turned to the Masonic Lodge for assistance. The Masons who volunteered were James Jones, a jeweler; William Longnecker, a livery stable owner; merchants John Braman and Robert Dunn; C. E. Frary, a Canadian carpenter; David Bradbury, a contractor; and general store owner B. A. "Gus" Whitney. Confederate Secretary of War James Seddon authorized Singer, now a captain, to form a company attached to the Bureau of Engineers to provide a special torpedo service. Captain Singer organized this unit as "Singer's Submarine Corps." Compensation would be 50 percent of the value of all ships and property or other Federal property destroyed.

Singer and Fretwell soon returned to Mobile to start placing these new underwater torpedoes (mines) in the bay. While there, they met three other Masons James McClintock, Baxter Watson, and Horace Hunley. These men had built two experimental submarines in the last two years. Known as *Pioneer I* and *II*, both had been lost. The five men became very good friends and formed a group known as "Singer's Secret Service Corps." The group decided to finance a new larger submarine, later to be known as the *CSS H. L. Hunley*.

In the late spring of 1863, the war turned against the Confederacy. Vicksburg was under siege and about to fall. Fretwell and Hunley were sent to Yazoo City, Mississippi to start placing torpedoes in the Yazoo River. The Yazoo River runs into Vicksburg and would be an easy route for Union gunboats. Soon after July 4, 1863, when Vicksburg surrendered, the Union ironclad "*Baron DeKalb*" headed up the Yazoo River where it came in contact with a torpedo. It quickly sank to the bottom of the river. Fretwell and Hunley returned to Mobile just in time to see

the new nine-man submarine launching. After several test runs and a demonstration of its ability to go under a barge while pulling explosives and blowing up the barge, it was ready. By July 31, 1863, General P. G. T. Beauregard ordered the new submarine, the *H. L. Hunley*, be shipped to Charleston, South Carolina. While the *Hunley* was in Charleston conducting test runs, it accidentally sank twice. The first time it killed five of the nine man crew. The second time all nine crew members including Captain H. L. Hunley died.

On February 17, 1864, the *Hunley* was ready for service with Lieutenant George Dixon as the skipper. She sank the Union ship, *The Housantonic*, and became the first submarine in the world to sink an enemy ship. However, the *Hunley* did not return to port. It is believed that the concussion knocked the crew unconscious, and they died from lack of oxygen. The *Hunley* was not found and recovered until 1995.

After overseeing torpedo operations on several rivers and coastal bays, Singer was rushed to Richmond, Virginia to oversee operations on the James River which led into Richmond. Singer designed drift mines for floating down the James River. In Mobile Bay, Union Admiral David Farragut decided to rush the bay, even knowing that there were over 100 torpedoes in the water with his famous statement, "Damn the torpedoes, full speed ahead." One of his larger iron ships, the *Tucumseh*, hit a torpedo, rolled on its side and went under the water in less than a minute.

A crew was sent to Shreveport to mine the water ways there, but it was too late. The Confederacy had been cut in half and could not survive. The war was soon over. The Singer Secret Service Corps had done everything in its power to help the Confederacy. It had sunk numerous Union boats and protected ports from being overrun. But at the end of the war these middle-aged Masons walked into a Union office in Lavaca where all this had started and simply signed parole papers.

In November of 2012, Mayor Jack Whitlow of Port Lavaca believed this story was about to be lost to history.

The Mayor proclaimed a "Lavaca Masonic Lodge Day" celebrating the 150th anniversary of the Battle of Lavaca, the Masons from Lavaca Lodge #36, and their accomplishments. There was a plaque installed to honor the Lodge and a big fireworks show. In a time when most politicians shy away from honoring Confederate men and women, the Mayor, City Council, and citizens of Lavaca were not intimidated to stand up for their heroes.

David Hudgins of Waxahachie, Texas is a member of the Ellis County Museum Board of Directors and co-founder of the Ellis County Veterans Appreciation Committee. He also serves as Chaplin of the O. M. Roberts Camp #178, Sons of Confederate Veterans. For more information, visit www.omroberts.com

SAMUEL HOUSTON CALDWELL

Surgeon, 46th Tennessee Infantry

Surgeon, 21st Tennessee Cavalry

By Peter J. D'Onofrio, Ph.D.

Samuel Houston Caldwell was born in Henry County, Tennessee on December 10, 1836, the second oldest son of Colonel Robert D. and Sarah E.

(Dupree) Caldwell. His father was a wealthy tobacco farmer who had settled in Henry County. Samuel had one older brother and one older sister, as well as four younger sisters and two younger brothers. In addition, he had three younger half-brothers.

In 1855, Samuel graduated from Cumberland University where he was a member of the Beta Theta Pi Fraternity. In 1858, he graduated from Jefferson Medical College in Philadelphia, Pennsylvania. After graduation, he set up practice in Paris, Henry Co., Tennessee and on December 24, 1860, he married Mary Rebecca (Molly) Thompson. Their union produced two daughters (Alice G. and Judith King) and two sons (William Howell and Robert D.).

When the War for Southern Independence broke, Dr. Caldwell enlisted in the 46th Tennessee Infantry. He was captured at Island No. 10 in the

spring of 1862. After his parole as a Prisoner of War on April 29, 1862, he served the remainder of the war as Surgeon to the 21st Tennessee Cavalry under General Nathan Bedford Forrest. His final parole was dated May 16, 1865 at Columbus, Mississippi.

At the conclusion of the hostilities, he returned to Paris, Tennessee where he again took up the practice of medicine. Dr. Caldwell died on November 14, 1917 of Chronic Nephritis (the inflammation of the kidneys caused by bacteria, streptococcal infections, diphtheria, septicemia, or toxic drugs such as mercury, arsenic, or alcohol). He is buried in the Paris City Cemetery along with his wife.

Submitted by Peter J. D'Onofrio, Ph. D., President, Society of Civil War Surgeons; www.civilwarsurgeons.org.

Reunion Medals For Sale

The Captain James Tyrie Wright MOS&B Chapter #6 still has some 2008 Reunion Medals for sale at a price of \$50.00, 2008 Reunion Programs for sale at a price of \$10.00, and 2013 Reunion Medals for sale at a price of \$40.00. Please also include \$2.00 each for postage and handling.

If interested, please make out your check to Capt. James Tyrie Wright MOS&B Chapter #6 and mail to:
J. Troy Massey, Adjutant, P O Box 536, Harrison, AR 72602.

If you have any questions, please send your inquiries of this items to mosbcg@cox.net or call 870-365-9273. Your participation is greatly appreciated.

MOS&B on Facebook

The national Military Order of the Stars and Bars has an official Facebook page that is available for all active MOS&B members to join. Anyone who requests membership will be approved after national membership is ascertained as the site is closed except to current official members. The site is not open for the general public to avoid misuse by those wishing to do harm to Southern heritage groups such as the MOS&B. The site is not a recruiting tool, but simply another communication tool for individual members and local Chapters and State Societies to keep in touch, share photographs and provide relevant information. In addition, up-to-date information about upcoming national meetings will be provided.

If you are interested in participating, simply go to Facebook, search *Military Order of the Stars and Bars* and then request membership through the simple directions on the site. We look forward to your participation.

Request for Annual Dues

Once again, dues season is upon us. The dues bills for each member should have already gone out whether you are an at large member or chapter member. Please consider paying them this month! All Chapter members need to send in their dues for their chapter, society, and national dues.

As a reminder, chapter adjutant's are to send the National Dues to MOS&B International, P.O. Box 56251, Virginia Beach, VA 23456. The dues for national are \$35.00 per year.

For all at-large members, please make out your check to "MOS&B" for \$35.00 and mail your payment to the address listed above.

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Patrick Cleburne Prints For Sale

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Please send your inquiries to purchase a copy of this print to mosbcg@cox.net. Your participation in this worthwhile project is greatly appreciated.

Request for Articles for the Upcoming 2015 Officer's Call Magazine

Please consider writing an article that can be included in future issues of the *Officer's Call*. Send your articles to the attention of our Editor General, Jeff Sizemore, whose email is swampeditor@yahoo.com.

Confederate Legacy Fund

The Legacy fund gives our members the opportunity to make a real difference. There is no better time than right now to make a statement for our values and our cause. The Confederate Legacy Fund is the vehicle that assures our relevance for generations to come.

We are extremely grateful to the members of The Confederate Legacy Legion of Merit. These men have chosen to support the Order by donating \$1000 or more to the Legacy Fund. We are indebted to all of our donors for their vision and their generosity.

The Confederate Legacy Fund is an important part of our over-all financial plan. The contributions that are made by our members will remain intact for perpetuity. Only the interest that is generated from the fund will be spent. Our expenditures are limited to scholarships and projects that will preserve and enhance our Southern Heritage. Currently these types of expenditures are paid for from our general fund. The income generated from the Legacy Fund will eventually pay for all of these types of expenditures.

MOS&B is a non-profit 501 (c) (3) corporation. As a result, all donations to the Legacy Fund are 100% tax deductible. In addition, many corporations will match the charitable donations made by its employees. Donating stocks is another excellent strategy for charitable donations. You can receive an income deduction for the full market value of a particular security. At the same time, you will avoid all capital gains tax on the transaction. There is no brokerage fee for this type of transaction.

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Confederate Legacy Legion of Merit neck ribbon and drop. A member may also qualify for the same award by utilizing one of our deferred payment plans.

Your generosity is most appreciated. Membership in the Confederate Legacy Legion of Merit will assure that there is always adequate funding for scholarships and Southern heritage projects. Please consider the Confederate Legacy Fund in your financial planning.

***78th Annual MOS&B
General Convention
Alexandria, VA
July 9th - 11th of 2015***

Plan on arriving Wednesday or Thursday and leaving Sunday, July 12. The convention will be held at the Monaco Hotel in the heart of Old Town Alexandria, George Washington's hometown and Robert E. Lee's boyhood home. The Monaco offers free shuttle service to and from Ronald Reagan National Airport about four miles away. The hotel stands on the site of the Marshall House famous for one of the first hostile encounters of the War for Southern Independence.

We have obtained a special rate for the convention. The Washington area is loaded with history and places to visit. Consider coming early or staying late to take advantage of the many attractions here. If you make your reservations early, the special rate will extend pre- and post-convention as well, if rooms are available.

***Tour Scheduled for
Friday Afternoon, July 10***

On Friday afternoon, two optional tours are offered. The first is to visit Christ Church within walking distance of the Convention Headquarters and the other tour is a visit to Arlington National Cemetery. We shall visit the Tomb of the Unknown Soldier, watch the changing of the guard, Jackson Circle, and Arlington House, where Robert E. Lee made his momentous decision to resign his commission from the United States Army on April 12, 1861.

At Arlington National Cemetery, a short ride from our headquarters hotel, is Jackson Circle, the burial site of over 400,000 military heroes and their families, including 482 Confederates: 46 officers, 351 enlisted men, 58 wives,

15 southern civilians, and 12 unknowns. They are buried in concentric circles around the Confederate Monument designed and sculpted by the world-renowned Moses Ezekiel, a VMI graduate who as a cadet fought with the Cadet Corps at the Battle of New Market. The graves are marked with headstones that are distinct for their pointed tops. Legend attributes these pointed-top tombstones to a Confederate belief that the points would "keep Yankees from sitting on them."

And of course Lee Mansion is located on the grounds of Arlington National Cemetery as well as the Tomb of the Unknown Soldier.

The Changing of the Guard at the Tomb is an experience never to be forgotten. An impeccably uniformed relief commander appears on the plaza to announce the Changing of the Guard. Soon the new sentinel leaves the

Quarters and unlocks the bolt of his or her M-14 rifle to signal to the relief commander to start the ceremony. The relief commander walks out to the Tomb and salutes, then faces the spectators and asks them to stand and stay silent during the ceremony.

Military Order of the Stars & Bars 78th Annual General Convention Alexandria, Virginia July 9-11, 2015

Convention Registration Form

Name & Title _____ Chapter _____
 Address _____ City/State/Zip _____
 Email: _____ Phone #: _____
 Guest(s) _____

Early Registration through March 31 _____ @ \$65.00 \$ _____

Regular Registration through May 31 _____ @ \$85.00 \$ _____

Late Registration after May 31 _____ @ \$105.00 \$ _____

Thursday, July 9

Commander General's Reception _____ @ \$60.00 \$ _____

Friday, July 10

Forrest Cavalry Corps Breakfast - pay at the door

Luncheon with Speaker – see supplemental information page _____ @ \$50.00 \$ _____

Arlington National Cemetery Tour – Arlington House, _____ @ \$40.00 \$ _____

Confederate Memorial, Tomb of the Unknown Soldier,

Changing of the Guard

or Christ Church Tour – church of George Washington and _____ @ \$15.00 \$ _____

Robert E. Lee

Saturday, July 11

Prayer Breakfast _____ @ \$35.00 \$ _____

Awards Luncheon _____ @ \$50.00 \$ _____

Commander General's Banquet _____ @ \$100.00 \$ _____

Ancestor Memorial (See Supplemental Information Sheet) _____ @ \$15.00 \$ _____

Total Enclosed (Check) \$ _____

Special dietary restrictions? - contact J.J. Smith 703-299-1725

Make check payable to: 2015 National Convention MOS&B

Mail to: J. J. Smith III, Adjutant, Virginia Society MOS&B, 401 Wilkes Street, Alexandria, VA 22314

Military Order of the Stars and Bars 78th National Convention

Alexandria, Virginia July 9-11, 2015

Thursday, July 9

Hotel Monaco Alexandria

General Executive Council meeting	1:00-3:00 pm
Registration in the Lobby	5:00-6:00 pm
Commander General's Reception – open bar, hors d'oeuvres	6:00-7:30 pm
Dinner on your own - Enjoy one of Alexandria's fine restaurants	

Friday, July 10

Hotel Monaco Alexandria

Registration in the Lobby	7:30-9:00am
Forrest Cavalry Corps Breakfast	8:00-9:00 am
Convention Opening Ceremony	9:00-9:30 am
Business Meeting	9:30-11:30 am
Luncheon with speaker	12:00 noon-1:45 pm
Arlington National Cemetery Tour	2:15-6:00 pm
Christ Church Tour	2:15-3:30 pm
Dinner on your own - Enjoy one of Alexandria's fine restaurants.	

Saturday, July 11

Hotel Monaco Alexandria

MOS&B Prayer Breakfast	8:00-9:00 am
Business Meeting	9:30-11:30 am
Awards Luncheon	12:00-2:00 pm
Free time in the afternoon.	
Commander General's Banquet	
Reception – open bar	6:00 pm
Dinner	7:00-9:00 pm

Hotel Reservations:

Call 1-800-368-5047. Ask for special rate for Military Order of Stars and Bars or

On-line: Go to their website - <http://www.monaco-alexandria.com> Click on *Reservations* - Select your dates - Key in 11580104146 in the *Meeting/Group Code* block - Click on *Check Availability*

You will be redirected to our exclusive reservations page with our Military Order of Stars and Bars rates

If you want to come earlier or stay later, you may be able to get the Stars and Bars rate depending upon availability. If are planning a pre or post attendance this summer, the sooner you make your reservation, the higher the likelihood you will receive the special rate for your entire stay.

Optional Tour Scheduled for Friday Afternoon, July 10

An option to the Arlington National Cemetery tour is offered: a tour of Historic Christ Church, located 3 blocks from Convention Headquarters. Both George Washington and Robert E. Lee were members and worshipped here. John Carlyle supervised its construction from 1767 to 1773. James Wren designed the church in the colonial style. Franklin Roosevelt and Winston Churchill visited the church on January 1, 1942, to commemorate World Day of Prayer for Peace.

General Samuel Cooper, his father, and son are all buried in the Christ Church Cemetery, but not in the churchyard. Christ Church also maintains a cemetery adjacent to the Alexandria National Cemetery, as do many other churches in Alexandria.

During the War, Lincoln sent a detachment to preserve the church. Only Union officers were able to worship there. It is probably the only church in the area that the Union did not gut. However, all the silver was missing when

the Union finally relinquished the church, and most of the headstones were gone and have never been found.

Among the burials in the church cemetery is the mass grave of thirty-four Confederate prisoners of war who died in local prison camps during the American Civil War. A memorial stone in the churchyard commemorates their deaths. The marker depicted was designed, built, and placed by the General Samuel Cooper Chapter of the Military Order of Stars and Bars.

Friday, July 10 Convention

Luncheon Presentation

Meet George Finley and march with him and his men into the mouths of the Union guns at Gettysburg. Pickett's Charge was the most dramatic event in the most dramatic battle of the most dramatic war in American history. Finley's story captures all the drama and illustrates the highest principles of leadership, courage, and character.

George Finley was a native Virginian who was one of a handful of Southerners who got over the stonewall at Cemetery Ridge. Finley noted that *"one company, a little to my right, numbering 35 or 40 men, was almost swept, to a man, from the line by a single shell"*. Finley's men tore down a snake rail wooden fence and fought their way to the infamous "angle in the stonewall" and held it for less than 30 minutes. Historians have termed this brief moment in time the "High Tide of the Confederacy." Here at the wall Finley took a musket and captured several Union artillerymen. While charging towards the cannon he captured, Finley could *"distinctly feel the flame of the explosion."*

Gradually, the weight of Union reinforcements overwhelmed Finley's men so he ordered them to surrender. While being led to the rear, Finley came upon

Confederate General Lewis A. Armistead on whose staff he had previously served. Presuming Armistead to be dead, Finley never stopped to console the dying Armistead and was filled with regret. While being held as a POW at Hilton Head South Carolina, as one of the "Immortal 600", Finley consoled many a fellow POW and made his decision to become a Christian Minister after the war. He eventually returned home and became the pastor of Tinkling Springs Presbyterian Church in Fishersville, Virginia.

Bill Young, our speaker-presenter on July 10, portrays Lt. Finley as he looked in the early 1900's. Not only is his outfit authentic, but also most of it is original. The black beaver top hat, black frock coat, vest, trousers, suspenders, high top shoes, and pocket watch are all from the 1890-1910 period. Finley's walking stick was a popular item of his day. It is topped with a pewter head of John Bull, the British equivalent to Uncle Sam, and bears the inscription, "Lt. George W. Finley, 56th Va. Inf. Rgt."

MOS&B National Awards Submittal Deadline Set for April 1, 2015

Annual MOS&B National Awards are presented once a year at the National Convention. Most are submitted by a member of the General Executive Council, Departmental Commanders or Society Commanders. These individuals have been sent the nomination forms and have been notified when nominations are due. Forms for submission have been furnished to all Society Commanders and will be made available on the National website. All nominations for awards must be submitted with written documentation that lists specific reasons for the nomination. Important - Please include the nominee's full name and mailing address, and if he is a member, also include his membership number (all nominations are placed in the members' respective MOS&B digital records file folder). Nomination forms should also contain the name and address of a contact person (usually the person submitting the nomination).

Chapter Commanders who wish to make nominations for National Convention Awards should work through their Society Commanders, utilizing the forms available on the national website. Nomination deadlines are important, as certificates must be printed and medals prepared. All interested parties should familiarize themselves with the nomination forms, and deadlines. This year the deadline is April 1, 2015.

The Military Order of the Stars and Bars Awards should be distinctive and special while recognizing those who have worked the hardest to advance the Order. Please keep this fact in mind when nominating members from your Chapter and Society.

All nominations shall be submitted through the MOS&B Chairman of Awards, Byron E. Brady, 1332 Garden Crest Circle, Raleigh, NC 27609 (byronbrady@aol.com). If submitting by email, the deadline for all awards nominations is April 1, 2015. If submitting through the USPS system, all letters must be postmarked no later than March 25, 2015.

Military Order of Stars and Bars Scholarships

To all MOS&B Chapters and Societies,

As you know, The Military Order of Stars and Bars has established a college scholarship program for genealogically proven: (1) descendants of Confederate Officers; (2) descendants of the Confederate Executive or Legislative branches of government; and (3) descendants of members of the Confederate States' legislatures, judiciary, and executive branches of government. The MOS&B Scholarship Program annually awards the merit based scholarships to worthy individuals who meet eligibility requirements and have been judged on information submitted by the applicant.

It is time to start considering candidates for the 2015 awards. All Chapters and Societies are encouraged to submit applications of worthy individuals for these scholarships. There are certainly many possible candidates among our active membership, active membership's children, grandchildren and friends.

The General Executive Council has determined that each Department scholarship awarded will be in the amount of one thousand dollars (\$1,000). The number of scholarships awarded each year will be determined by the GEC.

Please carefully read all the necessary information on the MOS&B national website.

<http://www.militaryorderofthestarsandbars.org/scholarship-program/>

Five copies of all requested material should be packaged together and mailed to:

MOS&B Scholarship Committee

c/o Gary M. Loudermilk

2801 14th Street
Brownwood Texas 76801

Applications must be postmarked no later than **March 1ST** to be eligible.

If you have questions, please contact Committee Chairman Gary M. Loudermilk at the above address or email: gmlhdl@harrisbb.com

Chapter and Society Newsletter Awards

Col. Walter Taylor Society Newsletter Award

This Annual National award will be presented to the State Society that regularly publishes a newsletter judged to be the most outstanding in the Order. Points are awarded based on: Format (15); Society and National News (30); Historical Content (20); Regular Publication Schedule (15); and Overall Interest and Appeal (20) for a total of 100 points.

To be considered for competition, one copy of each newsletter published must be submitted (either by hard copies, a PDF or on a CD) together to the Awards Chairman, Byron E. Brady, 1332 Garden Crest Circle, Raleigh, NC 27609 (byronbrady@aol.com) by April 1, 2015. Decisions of the judging are final. The publication schedule for competition purposes is from the month of the last National Convention (July, 2014) to April 1st of the following year (2015). Winners receive a certificate noting their achievement.

Judges for this award are Cain Griffin (SC), Ed Stack (VA), and Jeff Sizemore (FL).

Col. John Morton Chapter Newsletter Award

This Annual National award is presented to the Chapter publishing the newsletter selected as the outstanding Chapter publication in the Military Order of the Stars & Bars. To be considered for competition, one copy of each newsletter published must be submitted (either hard copy, a PDF, or on a CD) together to the Awards Chairman, Byron E. Brady, 1332 Garden Crest Circle, Raleigh, NC 27609 (byronbrady@aol.com) by April 1, 2015. Points are award-

ed based on: Format (15); Society and National News (30); Historical Content (20); Regular Publication Schedule (15); Overall Interest and Appeal (20) for a total of 100 points.

The publication schedule for competition purposes is from the month of the last National Convention (July, 2014) to April 1st of the following year (2015). Winners receive a certificate noting their achievement.

Judges for this award are Troy Massey (AR), Sig Reckline (CA), and Charles Smith (OK).

The Chaplain General's Thoughts - Earnest Prayer

By Raymond Holder

Continue earnestly with prayer, being vigilant with thanksgiving. Colossians 4:2

Our nation, the United States of America, has become and still is the most powerful country on the face of the earth. We have harnessed the power of the atom, control the commerce of the world, and still have the most powerful military in the world. So why is our reputation and influence as a nation waning around the world as it is according to many of the people we listen to in the different Medias such as television and newsprint? If this is true, how did we as a nation get to this point of apathy, meaning an attitude of not caring, for if we collectively cared as a people, there would be no question of our superior strength and influence around the world. What can we, you and I, do to affect the apathy of too many in our nation?

Earnest prayer is concentrated communication to our Lord God, not only at a set time of the day or night, but that also the way each of us live our minute to minute lives. 1 Corinthians 3:10 says "Whether, then, you eat or drink or whatever you do, do all the glory of God". My great challenge is simply, what prayer am I speaking to God in my actions, my thought process and what I say to others? Our prayers, whether personal or corporate, is our effort in putting our life more right with God and if this is earnest prayer, it has a tendency to cleanse us from what is not right in our individual lives.

The Holy Scripture, Galatians 3:26 tells us through the words of the apostle Paul, that we are the sons of God through faith in Jesus Christ. Real and effective prayer comes when you and I have a personal relationship to God through His son, Jesus Christ. Again, it's about the relationship with God. Once in a while, my father would tease me and say, "are you sure

you are my son". I would only have to look at him and know he was my father. I live a surrendered life to the will of my heavenly Father. Earnest prayer does that to my relationship to my Heavenly Father. Confession is the first act of earnest prayer. 1st John 1:9 says "If we confess our sins, He is faithful and just to give us of our sins, and to cleanse us from all unrighteousness". Our prayerful words of thanksgiving and praying for others, empowers our Godly relationship. Three years ago as a hospice chaplain I stood at the bedside of a 100 year old saintly lady who was in her last hours of life. I asked this saint of God why her Heavenly Father had bestowed the gift of a long life? She whispered with her limited breath of life, "Because I prayed for others". That's Earnest Prayer!

I believe the strength of our nation is measured through the prayers of its saint which are those of us who live surrendered lives to the Lordship of our savior, Jesus Christ. I found the following few words written by Robert E. Lee about prayer after the civil war or as many of us more accurately might say, "the war of northern aggression". It is still timely and true for today. "Knowing that intercessory prayer is our mightiest weapon and the supreme call for all Christians today, I pleadingly urge our people everywhere to pray. Believing that prayer is the greatest contribution that our people can make in this critical hour, I humbly urge that we take time to pray-to really pray.

Let there be prayer at sunrise, at noontime, at sundown, at midnight-all through the day. Let us pray for our children, our youth, our aged, our pastors, our homes, let us pray for our churches. Let us pray for ourselves, that we may not lose the word "compassion" out of our Christian vocabulary. Let us pray for our nation. Let us pray for those who have not known Jesus Christ and His redeeming love, for moral forces everywhere, for our leaders.

*"Let prayer be our passion.
Let prayer be our practice."*

Robert E. Lee

Cousin vs. Cousin (Part 1)

The Melancholy Journey of Robert Gibboney Baldwin

By Dr. Mark Denison Baldwin

America was in transition in 1836, the year that Robert Gibboney Baldwin was born, in Virginia. It marked the last year of the presidency of Andrew Jackson, but not Jacksonian Democracy which heralded the rise of the common man and Manifest Destiny. Early in

the year saw the Texas Revolution against Mexico, with defeats at the Alamo and Goliad, but eventual victory by the army under Sam Houston at San Jacinto on April 21, 1836.

Robert was the fourth son of Dennison David Baldwin and Jane Kyle (nee Gibboney) Baldwin.(1) Dennison Baldwin was of an old New England line dating back to 1638. Born in Poughkeepsie, New York in 1805, he had moved to southwest Virginia in the mid 1820s. He was employed by Thomas Gibboney, a dry goods merchant in Christiansburg, Virginia.(2) Gibboney and his wife Margaret (nee Kyle) had come to Virginia from near Omaugh, County Tyrone, in what is now Northern Ireland, around 1814-15. At the time of their emigration, they brought several children with them. Some sources allude one of their daughters, daughter Jane Kyle Gibboney, remaining in an Anglican convent school in Ireland, rejoining her family in the mid 1826.(3)

Jane and the young clerk, employed by her father, were enamored with each other. In December 1827, they were married in Wytheville, Virginia.(4) Soon, Dennison Baldwin would strike out on his own, perhaps with the assistance of his father in law, and become a dry goods merchant in several cities in southwest Virginia. Records of that period show that he had a brief association with several of his brothers in law, Robert and William Gibboney.(5) The economic and land booms of the early 1830's quickly collapsed in the Panic of 1837, the effects of which would last for almost a decade.

Around 1844, Dennison Baldwin suffered a series of business failures, leading him to mortgage all of his personal property, including two slaves, in a desperate effort to escape financial collapse. The measure proved futile; unable to keep up with the repayments, his property was forfeited.(6)

This was only the beginning of his eventual demise. Over the next several years, his physical and mental health would deteriorate to a point where he would undergo a forensic examination by Dr. Jacob Haller of Wytheville. (7) Based on findings of his evaluation, Dennison was committed to Western State Lunatic Asylum in Staunton, Virginia, in early 1850. Despite the best care, at that time, he would die of "paralysis" in the summer of 1855 and is buried in an unmarked grave on the grounds of the asylum. While his exact diagnosis at that time was unknown, it appears he may have suffered from "encephalitis lethargica," a form of Parkinson's disease. (8)

The Census of 1850 found a fourteen year old Robert Baldwin living in Wytheville with his mother and siblings. Although his father was hospitalized in Staunton, he was listed in this enumeration, under a separate column

with the comment "insane." Livings in the household were his mother Jane forty one, siblings Dennison sixteen, Phoebe sixteen, Elizabeth (Betty) thirteen, Mary ten, William eight, and Albert six. (9) Elder brother David Denison born 1828, had left home several years before, serving in the War with Mexico as a soldier in the Third Kentucky Regiment of Foot (Infantry) and later settling in Springfield, Ohio.(10) The other older brother, James Horace born ca 1830, was working as a clerk in Smyth County. (11) Following her husband's illness, Jane Baldwin was given a considerable amount of assistance by her brothers Robert and William Gibboney. Both men, along with another brother, Dr. James Gibboney, were quite prominent in the business and political landscape of antebellum Wytheville.(12) In subsequent year many of the Baldwin sons would be employed in the Gibboney's businesses.

By 1853, the United States was rapidly expanding, absorbing much of the western territories following the defeat of Mexico and the Treaty of Guadalupe Hidalgo in 1848. While settlers had been transiting west for decades to reach Oregon and California, now many of these territories were hoping for eventual statehood.

One of the most significant events in the history of the west was the discovery of gold at Sutter's Mill in California in 1848, unleashing the first "Gold Rush." Men and some families with dreams of riches plucked out of the streams, poured west only to face a multitude of obstacles en route and more upon arrival. Five years later, in 1853, a few had made their fortunes, while many more were scraping out an existence still hoping to get rich. Others had given up and sought other pursuits in the new country hoping to succeed. The territories's population had grown from about 15,000 in 1848 to over 300,000 by 1854. (13)

Settlers and prospectors coming from the back east had no easy travel options. The land routes posed challenges in distance, terrain, food and water supply and attack by those whose land it belonged to. This coupled with ever present illnesses and accidents, made the journey one for the stout of heart. An alternative, but also dangerous way, was by ship from either the east coast or Gulf coast to a number of ports on the California coast around to southern tip of South America. A shorter, but still risky path would be across the Isthmus of Panama. It would be five decades before the Panama Canal would be completed. Travelers would arrive at the east coast of Panama, go by cart and boat, or after 1855, railroad across the narrow strip of land and meet a ship sailing to California. During

this trip they were exposed to malaria, cholera, yellow fever along with dysentery, any of which could kill quite effectively. In 1851, Lt. Ulysses Grant made the crossing when he and seven hundred members of his regiment and their families travelled from Governor's Island in New York to a posting in California. (14)

By 1853, the gold frenzy began to wane, but not the migration to all points in the west. The delicate questions about fate of the new states in reference to slavery were temporarily abated by the Compromise of 1850, which admitted California to the Union as a "Free State." Back in Wythe County, Virginia, an enterprising young man name Robert Crockett had an idea to make some money and see the west by driving livestock across the plains and mountains to gold country in California. For this venture, he recruited several men from Wythe County to help him with the arduous task: William A. Cook, Charles Hounshell and Robert Baldwin. At some point, Jacob Nye from Wythe County and a man named Meredith joined the group. (15)

An interview with Robert Crockett done in 1901 and a series of recently discovered letters from William A. Cook, gives us a glimpse of their journey and life in California in the 1850s. (16) Crockett, Cook, Hounshell, and Baldwin left Wythe County on horseback in April of 1853 traveling down the Big Sandy to the Ohio River where they caught a riverboat which took them to St. Louis, Mo. From here, they crossed the Mississippi into Illinois in search of livestock to purchase for the enterprise. Within a short period of time, all of the men contracted malaria, which was endemic in much of the nation at that time. Waylaid by illness, they were set back while recuperating. Cook reveals in his letters that the illness intermittently incapacitated him for several months. (17)

Once their health improved, Crockett arranged for the purchase of 3,000 head of sheep, fifty milk cows, and twenty five mules. Other men joined the group, but once again, they were delayed, this time by the river floods of the spring melt. Once the flooding began to subside, they crossed the Mississippi at Hannibal, Missouri. They drove their herds across the state to St. Joseph where they were, once again, delayed by high waters of the Missouri River. Realizing they were further behind schedule they were anxious to get their investment back on the road. They were able to convince a hesitant river boat captain to ferry them across the swollen Missouri. For three days they went back and forth, taking the livestock to the other side. (18)

The illnesses and flooding delays had made them too late to try the northern trail that would lead them to northern California and the gold region, lest they get caught in the mountain blizzards of the Sierra

Mountains. The southern and less travelled route would take them across Kansas, New Mexico, southern Colorado, Utah, and southern Nevada and arrive in the small enclave of Los Angeles.(19)

Crossing the tan, dusty plains they passed immense black herds of buffalo and tribes of Indians. Their malarial fevers returned, but they were able to persevere. At one point, William Cook was left on the plains, possibly ill with fevers. Alone, except for his rifle to secure his food, and amidst hundreds of Indians, he was reunited with Robert Baldwin. Shortly after his arrival, Baldwin cooked some mutton for them to eat. Here, on the wide expanse of the plains, they were soon joined two men who had several mules; one of men was from their party. While Cook refers him as Samuel Nye, he is most likely Jacob W. Nye, from Wytheville.(20) The group journeyed on for seven days when they reached a settlement and here may have rejoined the main party.

In the Wasatch Mountain, south of present day Salt Lake City, Jacob Nye and several members departed from their friends, unburdened by livestock, to make the trek to San Francisco by the northern route. (21) He would eventually settle in Clark County, Washington, and be listed in the 1860 Census.(22) The rest of the party and their livestock headed southwest, following to Old Spanish Trail. Three days ahead of them was a topographical survey team for the proposed Central Pacific Railway survey, led by Captain Samuel Gunnison. Near Sevier Lake, his party was attacked by Paiutes, killing Gunnison and seven other member of their party on October 26, 1853. (23)

The Virginians avoided any hostile encounters as they made their way to California. Crossing the Mojave Desert, even in October was quite hostile; they finally came to the San Gabriel Mountains and the head of the river of the same name. Entering the mountains, they unhitched their teams, as the wagons would never negotiate the narrow passes nor the steep climbs. (24) Near one of their campsites, Charles Hounshell was killed when his rifle exploded. Crockett states that this happened on the slopes of the Sierra Nevada Mountains, but he may have confused as either the San Bernardino or San Gabriel Mountains were on their route. (25) The southern points of the Sierras were just north of them.

After seven harrowing months the party arrived in Los Angeles. Following the annexation from Mexico, Los Angeles was rapidly expanding with American sol-

diers, former soldiers, and settlers from back east. The gold rush had pushed the population even further. Crime was rampant with robbers, extortion artists, confidence men (and women), pickpockets, prostitutes, gamblers given free reign. Racial tension between the former Mexican residents and the new Anglo immigrants added to the lawlessness of the region. In the year of their arrival, the Los Angeles Police force was organized. Los Angeles provided much of the live stock and other staples for the northern regions and was a ready market for the men from Virginia. The herd was sold and the group went their own ways. How much Robert Baldwin, William Cook and others were paid for their efforts, is not known.

Crockett briefly explored some of the new land, but soon was on a ship back to the East Coast. Some of the men went north to the gold fields, while Cook and Baldwin remained in Los Angeles until at least October of 1854. From Cook's letter of September 1855,, he and Baldwin moved to San Francisco where Robert worked. Baldwin returned home by ship sometime before a letter of November 17, 1855. (26)

Wythe County must have seemed quite boring and mundane for young Baldwin as he returned home from his journey. In the next several years, he would move to Jeffersonville in Tazewell County, where his mother and several siblings lived. Here he took a position as a clerk, possibly for one of his Gibboney uncles who had businesses there. His elder brother David visited in 1857 following his exploits in Mexico, but would move on and settle in Springfield, Ohio. (27) Their mother Jane died of pneumonia in May of 1859. (28) He would be residing at the Union Hotel in Jeffersonville when he was enumerated in the 1860 Census. (29)

A year later, Baldwin and millions of other young men, North and South, would be swept up in an epic adventure, as a soldier in the Civil War.

All of the Baldwin brothers would see service in the war. Younger brother William was the first, shortly after the secession motion passed the Virginia Legislature in late April 1861. He was a corporal in the Wythe Grays, which became Company A of the Fourth Virginia Infantry Regiment.(30) Their older brother, David, residing in Ohio, would enlist in the Ninety-third Ohio Volunteer Infantry in 1862. (31)

Former Virginia governor and, more recently, former Secretary of War, John B. Floyd was commissioned as

a brigadier general and tasked with defending the western counties of Virginia, including those who wished to remain in the Union. Wytheville, Virginia, with its railroads and close proximity to the salt and lead mines, was chosen as the regional supply depot and training camp where regiments from southwest Virginia would be trained. Robert and William Gibboney, uncles to the Baldwin men, were commissioned as captains in the Quartermaster Corps for the depot. (32) Named Camp Jackson, for the late President, it soon burgeoned in late spring and early summer with recruits. (33) Men flocked to enlist for one year, hoping to serve before it was all over.

One of the newly mustered units, the Forty-fifth Virginia Infantry Regiment, was composed of companies of men from Tazewell, Wythe, Bland, Grayson and Carroll Counties. Perhaps it was his breadth of experience from his California excursion or his maturity that led to Robert G. Baldwin's election and commission as a second lieutenant in the West Augusta Rifles of Tazewell County. His youngest brother, sixteen year old Albert F. Haller Baldwin, would also serve with him. Their company would become Company G of the Forty-fifth, their date of enlistments was May 24, 1861. (34)

Henry Heth (pronounced Heath), West Point Class of 1847, has recently resigned his commission as a captain in the Regular Army to offer his services to his home state. Heth initially was sent to Richmond to assist in establishing the Confederate Army. In late May he was assigned to assist General Floyd in organizing and training a fighting force. Arriving at Camp Jackson, Heth was one of the few who had a professional military background. The men were issued uniforms, weapons, knapsack, blankets and other accoutrements of warfare. Given command of the Forty-fifth Virginia, Heth kept their days busy with drill, tactics, weapons training, inspections, guard duty, and camp duties. (35)

As a professional soldier, he was a strict disciplinarian, a trait needed to establish an effective fighting force. Heth was also from the Piedmont area of Eastern Virginia, both were reasons for the independent minded men from the Valley and mountains to resent him. If the men were disillusioned with Heth, Heth quickly became disillusioned with Floyd. He would later write: "I soon discovered that my chief was as incapacitated for the work he had undertaken as I would have been to lead an Italian opera." (36)

Complicating matters, Floyd's personal and political rival, former Virginia governor Henry Wise, was also

given a command and sent to defend the western counties. Much of their efforts for the next four months would see almost as much fighting between Floyd and Wise, as against the invading Yankees.

Soon, Robert and Albert would be joined in early July by their brother, Denison Butler Baldwin, recently commissioned as a first lieutenant in the Fifty-first Virginia Infantry Regiment. (37) Another brother, James Horace Baldwin likely served, but the specific information is sketchy. (38) Their cousin, John McCausland, Virginia Military Institute, Class of 1857, was commissioned as a Colonel in the Thirty-sixth Virginia Infantry Regiment. (39) Both units would be part of the Floyd-Wise forces and the Kanawha Campaign.

A week after going in to camp in Wytheville, they lost their first man to disease, over the next four years this invisible enemy would take a greater toll on both armies than cannons or bullets. When the regiment departed in July, they would leave over two hundred men, to recuperate from various illnesses. (40) ⁴⁰ However, all was not toil and trouble in those heady days of June and early July of 1861. Dress parades and frequent visits from locals and the young ladies from the Wytheville Female College did much to boost their spirits. The presence of the soldiers brought excitement to the town, still enthused about secession. (41)

Soon, those days would come to a close as the reality of war intruded. The Forty-fifth Virginia was one of the first regiments ordered to Camp Bee in Allegheny County. From there, Floyd's regiments marched to Lewisburg on August 4, then on to Sewell Mountain and then to Gauley Bridge. In early July, Henry Wise's Legion had burned the bridge in the face of a Union advance. (42)

Several companies of the Forty-fifth Virginia had their first taste of battle at Gauley Bridge on August 20. Facing off against the Eleventh Ohio Infantry, the Buckeyes fell back in the face of the charging rebels, only to trap them in an ambush. (43) Quickly withdrawing, the Virginians suffered four wounded. Several days later they surprised the Seventh Ohio Infantry at Kessler's Cross Lanes while they were eating their breakfast, scattering the surprised Yankees, taking a number of prisoners. (44)

Faced with prisoners to guard and maintain, the rules of exchange had yet to be established. A detail was assembled and ordered to escort the one hundred and four Yankees back to Richmond. In the guard were four of the Baldwin brothers, Denison, James, Robert and Albert. In a letter from Richmond, dated September 6, 1861, Denison Baldwin updates his wife Sallie on their mission.(45) By the middle of September, the Baldwins were back with their units on Sewell Mountain and may have missed the pivotal Battle of Carnifex Ferry.

An army under General William Rosecrans was advancing against the Confederates. If facing the Yankee invasion was not difficult enough, a war of memos continued between Generals Floyd and Wise with the War Department and President Jefferson Davis. These concerned issues of whose rank was superior and a host of trivialities and insults, both real and imagined. Retreated in the face of overwhelming Federal forces, Floyd achieved at least one victory, Henry Wise was ordered back to Richmond at the end of September; his command transferred to Floyd. (46) In their hurried retreat across the Gauley River, the men lost much of their equipment including tents and blankets.

September brought endless rain, skirmishes, retreat, disease, shortages in food, equipment and general suffering by all of the men, both officers and enlisted: not to mention the inept leadership by General Floyd. They encamped on Sewell Mountain while the Yankees pulled back. Floyd cautiously advanced in an attempt to coordinate and attack with General Robert E. Lee. After a week of slogging through the miserable road, shortages of food, and the poor conditions of the men, General Lee called off the offensive. Returning to Richmond, he left General Floyd in command. The misery continued. (47)

In late October, a number of the officers of the Forty-fifth Virginia had seen enough of unnecessarily suffering and neglect of their men, they submitted their resignations to General Floyd in an act of protest, with the hope that it would draw attention from Richmond. Offended at the men's protest, he ordered them to prepare to go back on the offensive. (48) One of those officers was Lieutenant Baldwin. When the men heard of the resignations, they begged the officers to rescind their requests. When the officers approached Floyd, he only let some of the officers, withdraw their documents. Robert was no so fortunate; he received his final pay of

\$240.00 after accounts were settled on November 8, 1861. (49)

The star crossed Kanawha Campaign ended in early December, when the remnant of Floyd's force straggled into the depot at Dublin, Virginia. Captain William Gibboney, Robert's uncle, arrived on December 24 with \$75,000 to give the men their first pay since May.(50) Colonel Heth was summoned to Richmond, promoted to brigadier general and assigned to Lewisburg. In a touch of irony, Baldwin's first cousin, Captain Gibboney's son, Albert Haller Gibboney, would serve as an aide and clerk to Henry Heth, beginning in April 1862 for the duration of the war. (51)

Returning to Wytheville, Robert's difficulties were not over. Brother Albert contracted typhoid fever in camp and died on December 19 at Red Sulphur Springs. (52) Denison Baldwin was home on leave and arranged for Robert to take a wagon to Giles Court House to bring Albert's body home for burial.(53) At the same time brother William, a corporal in the Fourth Virginia Infantry, Stonewall Brigade, was ill in a hospital in Winchester, but would survive. (54)

With his soldiering days apparently over it is unclear what employment he pursued. Uncles William and Robert Gibboney helped to maintain the army depot in Wytheville. On November 6, 1865, with the war seven months over, he took the Oath of Allegiance. (55) Robert and his brother James Horace Baldwin would marry sisters, Henrietta (Retta or Lettie) and Mary Jane Lofland. (56) From his marriage to Retta in 1862, five children were born: Louis, Denison, Eugene, Jane, and Cora. (57) His wife died of unknown causes; shortly after her death, he would marry her remaining sister Frances Elizabeth (Fanny) in 1882. This marriage did not produce any children. In the years following the war, his brothers resided in Wythe, Tazewell and Washington Counties and were successful in a number of business pursuits.

Robert's father in law, Smith Lofland, was listed in the 1880 Federal Census as a tin peddler.(58) As Robert was employed as a "drummer," an archaic term for a peddler; he may have been working in conjunction with his father in law. In 1883, things began to go horribly wrong in his life. His travels took him on the railways of the region. He began to drink heavily and was consuming morphine on a daily basis. (59) The Civil War was the first major conflict that saw the utilization of effective analgesic medication in the form of injectable morphine. Laudanum,

opium mixed with alcohol and consumed orally, had been available for sometime, however morphine was more potent, more so when injected. Opiate addiction had become so widespread after the war that it was commonly referred to as "Soldier's Disease." No doubt, many of the cases of opiate dependency and alcoholism in veterans were self medication for post traumatic stress disorder, referred to during the war as *nostalgia*. To further complicate the problem was the ready availability of laudanum and morphine, no prescription was needed as it was sold along with other patent medicines.

Robert Baldwin's downward spiral continued leading up to an incident on June 10, 1884 in Wytheville. His struggles with addictions had briefly improved in the spring of 1884 but returned with full vengeance. His normal well kempt and healthy appearance was gone as he appeared emaciated and disheveled. Clinging to his last vestiges of sanity, he became convinced that people were trying to follow him, poison him, and arrest him, common findings in the late states of addiction. These delusions led to Robert attempting to shoot a man in Wytheville on that day that he suspected of trying to harm him. (60)

Arrested by the sheriff, his aberrant mental condition required the evaluation of Dr. William P. Haller. A day after the attack, a formal commitment hearing was held in Wythe County. As prescribed by Virginia Law, three justices of the peace, Thomas J. Oberchain, William A. Umberger, and Thomas J. Moyers heard testimony from Dr. Haller about Robert's mental condition. Dr. William H. Ribble concurred with Dr. Haller's testimony and he was found to be "a lunatic." Based on the finding, he was ordered to be sent to Western State Lunatic Asylum in Staunton "until restored to sanity." (61) Ironically, almost thirty five years prior, in the same court, Haller's father, Dr. Jacob Haller examined and committed Baldwin's father, Denison David Baldwin to Western State in 1849. (62)

Nine days later, on June 20, 1884, an entry into the ledger, which would serve as his chart while a patient at Western State, summarized his recent circumstances. He was to be admitted for one year, his patient number was 3538. The admission entry was:

Admitted aged 48-Wythe-Married & has several children-

For several years past has been a "Drummer"-spending greater part of his time travelling & soliciting patronage on the several lines of rail-way-Consequently leading to an exposed & irregular life & subject to a variety of temptations under such circumstances, indulged freely in ardent

spirits, tobacco & finally acquired habit of using opium immoderately.

As was to be expected, he would follow these indulgences, his mind already predisposed by a Hereditary tendency, in consequence of his Father died an inmate of this asylum in 1855, his mind became seriously affected thusly more than 12 month[s] ago when he became entirely incapable of transacting himself & was kept in a passive condition in his brother's family.

His general state of health, somewhat infirm, especially the nervous system Doubtless due to the use of narcotics that he rest very well night& his appetite fair. (63)

An entry over a week later stated, "Today [he] has been indifferent to his surroundings, nothing to say -today he spoke kindly to a waiter, he says that he will not eat anything hereafter." In December he made an unprovoked assault on another patient, but by Christmas he was "behaving more courteously, better in language and manner." Nothing was recorded to indicate if any medication, the few ineffective ones available, or other treatments were utilized. (64)

Over the following eighteen years, aside from the usual aches and pains, it seems that he never was "restored to sanity" and able to be discharged, nor is no record of any furloughs. Robert was enumerated in the 1900 Census. (65) An entry from August 1890 states that he was allowed to walk in the front ground of the asylum and his behavior was more appropriate. Another entry from October 1894 found him, "Very happy & in excellent physical health. [He] imagines that under the institution is full of underground wires & machinery which is almost constantly working by thumping the wall & frame work to the covered [walk] way. [He] says he is just as well as he wanted to be." (66)

In November 1900, he was paralyzed on the right side of his face for several days, however this improved. This may quite well have been a transient ischemic attack, or "mini stroke." The next entry, eighteen months later on April 8, 1902 makes a reference to a recent "attack." Specifically what this entailed was not documented, but he had recently lost thirty pounds was, "full of delusions." He was much better, up and going to his meals again; he did not complain of pain, this is reiterated in the next entry four days later. But on April 15, he condition takes a turn for the worse as he is very weak and little appetite.

For this he is prescribed *Red Mist*. and two ounces of whiskey, three times a day. (67) No medication named "red mist" has been found. Red mist was nineteenth century term for extreme anger that clouded a person's judgment and this may have simply been a confusing entry.

A final entry on April 26, 1902 stated that he died at 4:15 that morning of Angina Pectoris. (68) There is no reference as to which family members were notified of his passing. Like his father, Robert Gibboney Baldwin was laid to rest in an unmarked grave on the grounds of Western State Hospital, his sad journey now ended. (69)

The author wishes to express his sincere thanks to Robert Lockett, Bev Hoch and Mary Kegley for their assistance in the preparation of this manuscript.

Endnotes

1. Mark D. Baldwin, Baldwin family history papers.
2. Mark D. Baldwin, "The Curious Case of Dennison David Baldwin Mental Illness in the Mid Nineteenth Century Virginia" *Retrospective, Journal of the Wythe County Genealogical and Historical Society*. 6, 2011, 25–32.
3. Robert Hudson Lear, *Thomas Gibboney and Margaret Kyle of Wythe County, Va. And Three Generations of Their Descendants* (Brunswick, GA: privately printed, 1991), 12.
4. Beverly Repass Hoch and Mary B. Kegley, *Wythe County Marriages 1790-1853* (Wytheville, VA: The Wythe County Genealogical and Historical Assoc., 2006), 12.
5. Mary B. Kegley, *The Early Adventures in the Town of Evansham, the County Seat of Wythe County Virginia 1790-1839*, vol. 4 (Wytheville, VA: Kegley Books, 1998), 76–77.
6. Montgomery County, VA, Deed Book 7, 43–45, a deed of trust between Dennison Baldwin and James F. Preston, 15 October 1842.
7. Dennison Baldwin papers, Archives of Western State Hospital, Staunton, VA, Office of Health Information (Medical Records), Western State, roll 3, 1–11.
8. Baldwin, "Curious Case" *Retrospective* 26–27.
9. 1850 U. S. Census (free schedule) Wythe County, Va. Roll M432_982, p 982, line 11, household 130.
10. *Report of the Adjutant General of the State of Kentucky: Mexican War Veterans* (Frankfort, Kentucky: Capitol Office, John D. Woods, Public Printer and Binder, 1889) 82-85, 94-97.
11. 1850 U. S. Census (free schedule) Smyth County, Va., Roll: M432_976; page: 211A; image 432.
12. Kegley, *Early Adventures*, 145–146.
13. http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/California#cite_note-52. Accessed 22 October 2013.
14. Ulysses S. Grant, *Personal Memoirs of U.S. Grant Volume 1*, (United States, Egyptian Press,) 96–97.
15. William A. Cook letter Number 3 dated 5 July 1854. The Connie Veneziano Collection, Wythe County Genealogical and Historical Association (WCGHA) Archives.
16. F. H. Terry, *Across the Rockies in '52 From Wythe County*. Interview with Robert Crockett. 1906. Typescript, WCGHA library, Wytheville.
17. Ibid.
18. Ibid.
19. Ibid.
20. 1850; Census Place: District 68, Wythe, Virginia; Roll: M432_982; Page: 267A; Image: 130.
21. Robert S. Lockett, "California Dreaming: From Wytheville to Gold Rush Country in 1853," *Retrospective, Journal of the Wythe County Genealogical and Historical Association*, 8, 2–16, 2012.
22. 1860 Census, Clark County, Washing; Roll:M653_1398; page:123; image:130.
23. Robert Kent Fielding, *The Unsolicited Chronicler: An Account of the Gunnison Massacre, Its Causes and Consequences*, (Brookline, MA, Paradigm Press, 1993) 187–188.
24. Terry, *Across the Rockies*.
25. Ibid
26. William A. Cook Letter 17 November 1855, Veneziano Collection, WCGHA.
27. "Mr. David T. Baldwin Dead," *Southwest Virginia Enterprise*, November 1902.
28. Thurman Robert Wilson and Ruth Boyd Wilson, *Tazewell County Death Records*, (Tazewell County, Virginia, 1993) 35.
29. 1860 Census, Western District, Tazewell, Va., Roll: M653_1381, page 900, image 412.
30. Mark D. Baldwin, Stephen A. Smoot, "The Wythe Grays, Harpers Ferry and Beyond," *Wythe County Historical Review*, 72, Winter, 2-18, 2009.
31. *Compiled Service Records of Volunteer Union Soldiers Who Served in Organizations from the State of Ohio, 93rd Ohio Volunteer Infantry Regiment*, David Theophilus Baldwin, M552, roll 4, *Compiled Service Record of soldiers Who Served in the War with Mexico from Kentucky*, M616, *Old War Index T316*, roll 18. National Archives and Records Administration (NARA)
32. *Compiled Service Records of General and Staff Officers and Non Regimental Enlisted Men*, William Gibboney, James Gibboney, NARA, M331, roll 105.
33. Mary B. Kegley, *Wythe County, Virginia, A Bicentennial*

History, (Marceline, MO, Walsworth Publishing 1989), 189–190.

34. *Compiled Service Records of Confederate Soldiers Who Served in Organizations from the State of Virginia, 45th Virginia Infantry Regiment*, Robert Gibboney Baldwin, Albert Haller Baldwin, NARA M324, roll 884.

35. Henry Heth, *The Memoirs of Henry Heth*, James L. Morrison, editor, (Westport, CT, Greenwood Press, 1974), 151–152.

36. Ibid

37. *Compiled Service Records of Confederate Soldiers Who Served in Organizations from the State of Virginia, 51st Virginia Infantry Regiment*, Denison Butler Baldwin, NARA M324, roll 927.

38. Letter from Denison Butler Baldwin to Sallie Baldwin, Richmond, Va., 6 September 1861. Original in the special collections Virginia Polytechnic Institute Library, Blacksburg, Va.

39. *Compiled Service Records of Confederate Soldiers Who Served in Organizations from the State of Virginia, 36th Virginia Infantry Regiment*, John McCausland, NARA M382, roll 6.

40. J. L. Scott, *45th Virginia Infantry*, (H. E. Hun, Lynchburg Va., 1989) 5-6.

41. Letter from Albert Gibboney to Sallie Bogle, 30 June 1861, Original in the collection of the Wythe County Historical Society.

42. Scott, *45th Virginia*, 6.

43. Ibid, 7.

44. Ibid, 8.

45. Letter from Denison Butler Baldwin to Sallie Baldwin, Richmond, Va., 6 September 1861. Original in the special collections Virginia Polytechnic Institute Library, Blacksburg, Va.

46. Scott, *45th Virginia*, 10.

47. Ibid.

48. Denison Butler Baldwin letter to Sallie Baldwin, Below Fayette court House, 23 October 1861. Original in the special collections Virginia Polytechnic Institute Library, Blacksburg, Va.

49. Scott, *45th Virginia*, 11.

50. *Compiled Service Records of Confederate Soldiers Who Served in Organizations from the State of Virginia, 45th Virginia Infantry Regiment*, Robert Gibboney Baldwin, NARA, M324, roll 884.

51. *The Official Records of the War of the Rebellion*, Series 1, supplement, volume 52, part II, 252, Washington D.C.; U. S. Government Printing Office, 1898.

52. *Compiled Service Records of the Confederate Soldiers Who Served in Organizations from the State of Virginia, 22nd Virginia Infantry (First Kanawha Regiment)*, Albert Gibbony [sic], NARA, M382, roll 21.

53. *Compiled Service Records of Confederate Soldiers Who*

Served in Organizations from the State of Virginia, 45th Virginia Infantry Regiment, Albert Haller Baldwin, NARA, M324, roll 884.

54. Letter from Denison Butler Baldwin to Sallie Baldwin, Wytheville, Va. 23 December 1861. Original in the special collections Virginia Polytechnic Institute Library, Blacksburg, Va.

55. Letter from James H. St. Clair to Sallie Bogle. Camp Stevenson, Winchester Va., 28 December 1861. Original in collection of the Wythe County Historical Society, Wytheville, Va.

56. Robert G. Baldwin. Loyalty Oath, 6 November 1865. Accession 40526, Personal papers collection, The Library of Virginia, Richmond, Va. 23219.

57. Janie Dillon and Mary B. Kegley, *Wythe County Marriages 1854–1866*, (Wythe County Genealogical and Historical Association, Wytheville, Va., 2007) 86.

58. 1880 Census, Goodson, Washington County, Va., roll: 1394, page 116C, image 096.

59. Ibid

60. Record of Western State Hospital, 1825–2000, accession number 41253, admission numbers 3086–41253, volume 249, patient 3538, Robert Gibboney Baldwin, State government records collection, The Library of Virginia, Richmond, Virginia.

61. Ibid.

62. Ibid

63. Dennison Baldwin papers, Archives of Western State Hospital, Staunton, VA, Office of Health Information (Medical Records), Western State, roll 3, 1–11.

64. Western State Records, Robert G. Baldwin

65. Ibid

66. 1900 Census, Staunton City, Virginia; roll 1740; microfilm 121740; page 4A.

67. Western State Records, Robert G. Baldwin

68. Ibid

69. Ibid

70. <http://files.usgwarchives.net/va/augusta/cemeteries/westshosp.txt>, accessed 12 December 2012.

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